

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
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School of Health and Life Sciences

THE EFFECT OF MENTAL FATIGUE ON
TIME TO EXHAUSTION DURING
DIFFERENT INTENSITIES OF CYCLING
EXERCISE

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A thesis submitted to University of the West of Scotland in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science (MRes)

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Declaration

I confirm i) that whilst registered as a Master by Research candidate at University of the West of Scotland, I have not been enrolled as a student at any other institution of higher education, ii) that this thesis does not contain any material that has been previously submitted for an academic award, and iii) that this work is solely the result of my own efforts, except where acknowledged.

Alessio Marciano

Abstract

Purpose. It has been demonstrated that mental fatigue (MF) impairs exercise tolerance. Although some authors have hypothesised that the higher the exercise intensity the lower the impact of MF, it is unclear whether physiological determinants of endurance performance at different intensity domains are modulated by the ergolytic effects of MF. Thus, we evaluated the effect of MF on time to exhaustion (TTE) during cycling at heavy- and severe-intensity exercise. **Methods.** Twenty-three highly trained endurance subjects (26 ± 5 yr; 71 ± 6 kg) performed an incremental cycling test to exhaustion immediately followed by a 2-minute all-out test, enabling the detection of the Critical Power (CP). Each subject underwent four testing sessions on different days, involving either 45-min of intervention followed by constant work rate cycling exercise to exhaustion at heavy (90% CP; CWR_{HVY}) or severe (110% CP; CWR_{SEV}) intensity. During interventions, documentary watching (Control) was used as a control task and a continuous choice reaction task (Simon) was used to induce MF. The time-course of reaction time (t_r) and error-rate (ER) during SIMON was monitored. Subjective rating of MF, assessed by VAS scale (VAS-M), and mental workload (TLX), evaluated by NASA TLX questionnaire, were collected before exercise. Cardio-respiratory and metabolic responses to exercise were monitored. **Results.** Maximal oxygen uptake ($\dot{V}O_{2max}$) and maximal work-rate were 53.5 ± 8.0 ml·min⁻¹·kg⁻¹ and 368 ± 65 W, respectively. CP was 279 ± 58 W. CWR_{HVY} and CWR_{SEV} time to exhaustion were significantly lower after Simon (CWR_{HVY} : 1766 ± 907 s; CWR_{SEV} : 438 ± 270 s) compared to Control (CWR_{HVY} : 2004 ± 903 s; CWR_{SEV} 393 ± 248 s; both $p < 0.05$), whereas physiological responses to exercise were not different between conditions. No significant differences in performance loss due to MF between intensity domains were observed (CWR_{HVY} 10.7%; CWR_{SEV} 8.2%, $p > 0.05$). VAS-M score and TLX were significantly higher after Simon than Control (VAS-M: Control 8.3 ± 4.4 vs Simon 13.2 ± 4.3 , $p < 0.01$; TLX: Control 23.3 ± 22.9 vs Simon 74.5 ± 15.4 $p < 0.01$). During Simon, t_r did not change over time ($p > 0.05$) but ER increased significantly ($p < 0.01$). **Conclusions.** Completion of 45 min cognitive task induced significantly higher ratings of MF and mental workload, decreasing exercise tolerance to a similar extent in both heavy and severe domains. Thus, performance impairments induced by mental fatigue do not seem to be exercise-intensity dependent. Our results suggest avoiding tasks that may induce MF before activities and competitions irrespectively of their intensity.

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Abbreviation

ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
O ₂	Oxygen
$\dot{V}O_2$	Oxygen uptake
$\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$	Maximal oxygen uptake
\dot{Q}_aO_{2max}	Maximal flow of O ₂ in arterial blood
CP	Critical Power
CV	Critical Velocity
W'	Finite amount of work that can be done above critical power
EEG	Electroencephalography
ACC	Anterior Cingulate Cortex
tDCS	transcranial Direct Current Stimulation
fMRI	functional Magnetic Resonance Imagery
AX-CPT	AX Continuous Performance Test
SIMON	Simon Task
VAS	Visual Analogue Scale
BRUMS	Brunell Mood State scale questionnaire
TLX	NASA Task Load Index questionnaire
t _r	Reaction Time
ER	Error Rate
RPE	Rating of Perceived Exertion
RST	Ramp Sprint Test
CWR	Constant work rate exercises
HVY	Heavy

SEV	Severe
MOOD	Mood questionnaire
VAS-M	Perception of mental fatigue questionnaire
W_{GET}	Power at gas exchange threshold during ramp incremental exercise
W_{peak}	Peak power output during ramp incremental exercise
TTE	Time To Exhaustion exercise
$\dot{V}E$	Pulmonary ventilation
$\dot{V}CO_2$	CO ₂ output
B_f	Breath frequency
V_t	Tidal Volume
HR	Heart Rate
$[La]_b$	Blood lactate concentration
y_{BAS}	$\dot{V}O_2$ baseline
A_f	$\dot{V}O_2$ amplitude between the y_{BAS} and the steady state
TD_f	Time delay of the fundamental phase
τ_f	Time constant of the fundamental component
S	Slope
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
SD	Standard Deviation
SEM	Standard Error of the Mean

1.0 - Introduction

Understanding the factors which influence endurance performance is crucial for the development of therapeutic and athletic interventions aimed at enhancing exercise tolerance. Clinical health is positively affected when individuals exercise and improve their exercise tolerance and athletes' performances benefit from pushing their physical limits forward. To date, it is not yet clear which factors are real 'limits' to exercise tolerance but some hypotheses based on experimental results have been proposed.

Traditionally, investigations of exercise endurance have been focused on the biological aspects of human performance. Indeed, since the pioneering works of A.V.Hill on muscular physiology, numerous physiological theories have been developed to describe the factors that limit human performances, characterizing fatigue-related phenomena from systemic to muscular levels (Hill, 1932). More recently, cardio-respiratory components (Poole et al., 1988) and intracellular metabolite alterations have been proposed to limit tolerance according to exercise intensity (Black et al., 2017, Goulding, Roche and Marwood, 2018) but these models fail to explain the role of the mind within exercise tolerance and endurance performance. As a result, researchers have begun to examine endurance performance more holistically integrating both biological and psychological aspects to explain how endurance exercise is regulated (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b).

The Finnish Olympic champion Paavo Nurmi once said, "Mind is everything. Muscle – pieces of rubber: All that I am, I am because of my mind." Indeed, research findings suggest that the mind plays a principal role in exercise tolerance and many psychological components have been shown to influence endurance performances (McCormick, Meijen and Marcora, 2015). The first work suggesting the negative effects of prolonged mental demands on exercise dates back to 1891 when Professor Mosso showed that muscle force was reduced after attending a long lecture (Mosso, 1891). Since then, extensive literature has investigated the effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance (Brown et al., 2020). It has been suggested that mental fatigue can lead to impaired behavioural and physical performances (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2006a, Boksem and Tops, 2008). Worsening performance seems to be associated with negative changes in the perception of effort and motivation that are both described as limiting factors in endurance exercise (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b).

Some recent literature reviews propose that the detrimental effects of mental fatigue on exercise performance are intensity mediated. More specifically, systematic reviews of the literature have suggested that the higher the exercise intensity the lower the impact of mental fatigue (van Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018). However, the review included heterogeneous groups of different study designs and cohorts of participants with different fitness statuses, and the intensity

dependent effects of mental fatigue are far from established. This is important as exercise intensities have been divided into aerobic (endurance), anaerobic, and maximal exercise and different physiological limiting factors occur at different aerobic exercise intensities. To date, no single study has directly tested the effects of mental fatigue on different endurance intensities using a within subject design. Indeed, a more comprehensive understanding of how mental fatigue affects endurance tolerance according to aerobic exercise intensities is needed. Therefore, the current thesis presents an experimental study aiming to evaluate the effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance in different exercise intensity domains.

2.0 – Endurance performances

Different types of sport training and competition are wide ranging in duration, intensity, and their associated mental and physical demands. Endurance exercises are defined as muscular and whole-body activities that imply prolonged exercise that generally last for more than two minutes (Burnley and Jones, 2007) and are characterized by a substantial and sustained energy transfer from oxidative pathways. From a physiological point of view, endurance performance can involve activities that range from very low intensity, like walking or repetitive housework, to severe intensity exercise such as uphill cycling, requiring maximal cardio-respiratory responses. Several factors modulate an individuals' ability to sustain a given power or velocity within this extremely wide spectrum of intensities and exercise interruption usually occurs when participants are no longer able to generate the power output required by the task despite their maximal voluntary effort (Gandevia, 2001). Task failure is often referred to as the “point of fatigue” or “exhaustion” and is determined according to different physiological and psychological factors.

Numerous physiological models describing the principal factors involved in human performance (Bassett and Howley, 2000) and their limiting factors (Gandevia, 2001) have been proposed through the years. Indeed, different limiting factors occurring within specific endurance exercise intensity domains have been described (Black et al., 2017). Conversely, the psychobiological model of exercise tolerance (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b), postulates that exercise tolerance is principally dictated by an individual's perception of effort and the potential motivation. Many factors have been described to affect these psychological parameters and including mental fatigue, which has been shown to influence exercise tolerance with no effects on both the time-course and the maximal physiological parameters during exercise (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009).

Several previous studies have been conducted to investigate the limits of endurance performance, being mainly focused either on physiological determinants or psychological factors. However, more complex investigations which include both psychological and physiological aspects are needed in order to fully understand how endurance performance is influenced by the interaction between physiological and psychological variables (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, McCormick, Meijen and Marcora, 2015). In the next section the physiological limits of exercise tolerance will be described in detail, before a critical discussion of how psychological factors, such as mental fatigue, can modulate exercise tolerance.

2.0.1 – Limiting factors: physiological models of exercise tolerance

The physiological determinants of endurance tolerance have been extensively investigated for almost one hundred years, starting from the classical physiological model described during the 1920s by Prof. AV Hill (Hill, Long and Lupton, 1924a) up to the more complex and expanded models proposed in the last 20 years (Bassett and Howley, 2000, Joyner and Coyle, 2008, Black et al., 2017, Goulding et al., 2021). The general hypothesis in exercise physiology is that highly motivated people terminate endurance exercise when they are no longer able to produce the required velocity or power despite maximal voluntary effort due to a fatigued system (Hill, Long and Lupton, 1924b, Gandevia, 2001, Hepple, 2002, Burnley and Jones, 2018). The source of fatigue is dependent on the exercise intensity and duration and exercise in-tolerance is dictated principally by the in-capacity of the cardio-respiratory and the neuromuscular systems to meet the exercise demand.

During exercise, adenosine triphosphate (ATP) must be supplied as fast as it is used to maintain a specific work rate or a defined velocity. To ensure the continuation of muscular work when exercise duration increases, the energy source progressively shifts from anaerobic sources toward the oxidative phosphorylation system, consequently reflecting the rate at which O_2 is used to create ATP. Thus, measuring O_2 consumption ($\dot{V}O_2$, at the level of the mouth) during exercise is a good indicator of endurance capacity because the higher the $\dot{V}O_2$ the higher amount of energy will be transferred to produce ATP during exercise. Maximal $\dot{V}O_2$ ($\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$) can be defined as the highest rate at which O_2 can be utilized by the body during maximal and prolonged exercise (Bassett and Howley, 2000), and it is considered a key factor in endurance exercise (Hill, Long and Lupton, 1924a).

The physiological model proposed by Wagner (Wagner, 1993) proposed that two primary inhibitors limit the maximal conductance of O_2 from the ambient air to the muscle mitochondrion. The first limit resides within the cardiovascular system where O_2 is carried through the alveolar capillary to arterial blood and it binds to hemoglobin, defining the maximal flow of O_2 in arterial blood (\dot{Q}_aO_{2max}). Then, the second limit occurs at the muscle capillary-myocyte interface level when O_2 flows from capillary to contracting myofibers according to Fick principle and the diffusion-perfusion interaction equation, setting $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$ (Wagner, 1993, di Prampero, 2003, Ferretti, 2014). According to the present model and subsequent experimental testing, convective O_2 transport within the cardiovascular system limits O_2 availability to muscle at sea level (Wagner, 1992, Richardson et al., 1999). Indeed, the ability of the heart to pump O_2 -enriched blood towards exercising muscle accounts for 70% of the total limitations of $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$ (di Prampero and Ferretti, 1990). As a consequence, subjects performing endurance exercise have to stop when the O_2 supply to the muscle is no longer sufficient to match the energetic demand. This phenomenon occurs when maximal

predicted heart rate and maximal cardiac output are reached (Wagner, 1996). Indeed, interference of conductance of any step in the pathway from ambient air to muscle mitochondrion will predictably affect O₂ delivery and consequently exercise tolerance. As an example, training elicits opposite effects compared to those induced by inactivity, like bed rest. The observed increase in training is accompanied by an increase in \dot{Q}_aO_{2max} , muscle capillary density and mitochondrial volume and function, determining an increase in O₂ availability (Ferretti, 2014).

The oxygen cascade from the mouth to the muscle can be considered the physiological basis for understanding $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$ and maximal exercise tolerance, whereas endurance performance usually includes prolonged exercise performed at intensities lower than $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$. As clearly summarized by Burnley and Jones, endurance exercise intensities can be divided into four different intensity domains and different limiting factors have been characterized in relation to each domain (Burnley and Jones, 2007, 2018, Black et al., 2017, Goulding et al., 2021). The **moderate domain** includes exercise intensities that go from resting value up to lactate threshold, or gas exchange threshold (Beaver, Wasserman and Whipp, 1986) and is limited to exercise that lasts more than 3-4 hours. In this domain, the $\dot{V}O_2$ change over time from rest to exercise, namely $\dot{V}O_2$ kinetics, follows a mono-exponential increase up to a steady state that is attained within 2-3 minutes of exercise onset. Accordingly, exercise tolerance at a moderate intensity has been shown to be primarily physiologically limited by muscular glycogen depletion (Black et al., 2017). When energy demand increases above the lactate threshold, the exercise intensity enters into the **heavy domain** which includes exercises that go up to the lactate turning point or the critical power/speed. In this domain, the rise of $\dot{V}O_2$ is similar to the one observed in the moderate intensity domain until the first steady state phase. After that, $\dot{V}O_2$ starts again to mono-exponentially increase and it goes up to a second higher steady state, showing an increase of the energy cost of the exercise (i.e. slow component). Heavy exercise can usually be endured for between 30-45 minutes and 3-4 hours and subjects stop when both muscular glycogen is depleted and the muscular homeostasis is perturbed (Black et al., 2017). Above the heavy domain, exercise intensity is namely identified as **severe (domain)** and time-to-exhaustion decreases following a hyperbolic function when work rate increases. The hyperbolic model was summarized by Jones and colleagues (Jones et al., 2010) and it is built on the historical foundations of the critical power (CP; or velocity CV) concept, that is the highest sustainable rate of aerobic metabolism (Hill, 1993) occurring at a similar work rate to the previous described lactate threshold (also named lactate turning point)(Poole et al., 2020). This relationship is consistent across different modes of exercise and is described only by two parameters: CP or CV, that define the asymptote for power or velocity, and the curvature constant (W') of the relationship such that $t = W'/(P - CP)$ (MONOD and SCHERRER, 1965). W' represents a finite amount of work that can be done when exercise is

performed to task failure within the severe domain (Jones et al., 2010). According to the classic interpretation, W' represents the amount of work derived through phosphorylation using PCr and glycogen (Jones et al., 2010) and sometimes is inaccurately termed “anaerobic work capacity”. In the **severe domain**, no steady state is attainable for any physiological parameter and $\dot{V}O_2$ increases linearly up until the maximal value. Subjects exercising in the severe domain can endure between 2 minutes and 45 minutes and exhaustion occurs when a critical metabolic perturbation is reached (Black et al., 2017). The last domain, defined as **extreme exercise**, is characterized by all the exercise intensities above the maximal work rate that is able to achieve $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$ and exhaustion usually occurs in less than 2 minutes (Burnley and Jones, 2018). The extreme domain is not considered as a part of the endurance intensities because the metabolism involved during this type of exercise relies principally on the glycolytic pathway which reaches exhaustion quickly.

It is clear that exercise responses are mediated by exercise intensity and every practical intervention that is able to improve one of the previously described limiting factors should be able to improve exercise tolerance. Among that, exercise training is the most used tool to improve physical capacity and exercise tolerance. Indeed, an enormous variety of physical training methods have been proposed to improve performance, reduce morbidity and sedentarism. Most of these methods have been demonstrated to increase $\dot{V}O_{2MAX}$, maximal cardiac output as well as increase muscle capillarity and mitochondrial function, whether exercise protocol was continuous or with high-intensity intervals (Ekblom et al., 1968, Blomqvist and Saltin, 1983, MacInnis and Gibala, 2017). Conversely, all the previous listed parameters deteriorate when subject become inactive (Saltin et al., 1968). Thus, it is clear that different exercise intensities elicit different, and reliable, physiological responses, and based on the improvements that should be achieved different exercise prescription must be made.

This physiological view only reflects one side of the coin when we speak about limiting factors in endurance performance. Indeed, different fields of investigation demonstrate that endurance performances could be improved using drugs or ergogenic aids (Wagner, 2012), using engineered technical equipment (Nielsen et al., 2022) and many psychological interventions (McCormick, Meijen and Marcora, 2015). The next section will be focused on the integration of different frameworks that describe exercise tolerance according to the integration of psychological and physiological factors, aiming to clarify to the researchers and practitioners how prolonged exercise is regulated.

2.0.2 – Limiting factors: psychobiological model of exercise tolerance

As previously described, motivated people are thought to terminate endurance exercise when fatigue occurs and they are no longer able to keep the pace with the exercise demand (Hill, Long and Lupton, 1924, Gandevia, 2001, Hepple, 2002, Burnley and Jones, 2018). From a physiological point of view, it is expected that during a constant work rate exercise the maximal power (or: velocity, work-rate) decreases linearly over time, due to the progression of fatigue, and exhaustion occurs when maximal power is equal to the power required by the task. After this crossover point exercise becomes theoretically unsustainable because the maximal power is expected to drop below the power necessary to continue the exercise. However, findings which contradict this hypothesis have been reported. Several studies have demonstrated that participants were able to generate higher power than the power required by the precedent task in the exact moment they get exhausted (Marcora and Staiano, 2010b, Staiano et al., 2018, Ferguson et al., 2022, Morales-alamo et al., 2022). These findings challenge the assumption that the progression of fatigue directly causes exhaustion during endurance exercise calling into question the sole focus on the physiological limiting factors previously described. Fortunately, a framework describing the psycho-biological processes underpinning endurance exercise tolerance has been proposed to explain why and how endurance performance is affected by cognitive processes (McCormick, Meijen and Marcora, 2015).

To fully understand how exercise is regulated during sports, in 2010 Marcora proposed the psychobiological model of exercise tolerance which examines endurance performance as a goal-directed behaviour (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b). He suggested that performance can be explained by psychological and behavioural factors instead of considering human as biochemical engine. This model explains that exercise is limited at a psychological level, based on motivation and perception of effort, and at a biological level where neurobiological processes are involved. According to Marcora, the limit of tolerance is the result of the perception of effort and potential motivation. The perception of effort is defined as the conscious sensation of how hard and strenuous the physical task is (Marcora, 2009) and it is usually measured using the Borg's scale (Borg, 1998). Potential motivation, derived from the Brehm's Motivational Intensity Theory (Brehm, 1989), is defined as the amount of effort a person is willing to exert in the task. When success in the task is perceived to be impossible or excessively difficult, motivation intensity reduces and then people will stop expending effort in the task (Wright, 2008). At the biological level, the model describes that perception of effort is generated by brain processing at any given time during exercise. Thus, while muscle fatigue progresses during exercise, central motor command is increased to maintain the required force and reflect a progressive increase in neural signals processed by the brain to generate perception of effort, or changes in the way the brain processes these neural signals (Marcora, 2008).

Brain processing can be described by the corollary discharges within premotor and motor areas of the cortex which then drives the working muscle (Marcora, 2009). The perception of effort is reflected within the magnitude of the corollary discharges which increase with rising exercise demand and muscular fatigue (Marcora, 2019).

The psychobiological model suggests that changes in physiological parameters are considered to be key factors in improving or worsening endurance performances, but they act indirectly modifying the perception of effort. Moreover, endurance performance can be practically modified by influencing the perception of effort or motivation. Indeed, endurance training has been shown to improve different cardio-respiratory parameters and consequently to reduce the perception of effort when the same work rate performances are carried out (Ekblom and Golobarg, 1971). According to this approach, the metabolic improvements gained during training directly improve the perception of effort and consequently extend exercise tolerance and performances. Furthermore, any other physiological and/or environmental factors, are thought to indirectly affect exercise tolerance, if they influence the perception of effort. This model also predicts that changes in potential motivation will lead to modifications in exercise tolerance. For example, competition and monetary rewards can increase exercise tolerance or performance (Boksem and Tops, 2008, Lorist et al., 2009, Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009). One psychological factor which has been identified to be influential to the perception of effort, motivation and endurance performance is mental fatigue.

2.1 - Mental Fatigue

Endurance performance is both physically and mentally demanding. Fatigue is a multidimensional phenomenon that limits physical tolerance and includes physical and mental cues. Despite a universal definition of fatigue remaining elusive, the specific term mental fatigue has been described as a psychobiological state that people experience after prolonged period of demanding activities (Boksem and Tops, 2008). Mental fatigue is characterized by subjective sensation of “tiredness” and “lack of energy” and it has been associated with impaired cognitive and behavioural performances (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2005, Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005, van der Linden and Eling, 2006)

Mental fatigue is a common experience for many and has implications for several aspects of daily life. It has been investigated in a wide variety of contexts, but the largest part of the literature is focused on the factors which cause this phenomenon and its characteristic responses (Matthews and Hancock, 2017). The most common activities that lead to mental fatigue are repetitive and prolonged cognitive tasks. Indeed, such tasks that have been created and standardized within laboratory settings to understand the mechanisms behind this phenomenon (O’Keeffe, Hodder and Lloyd, 2020). Certain

cognitive-demanding daily life activities have been demonstrated to lead to mental fatigue, as well as sleep deprivation, drugs, environmental stressors, and screen-time (Owens, 2007). Indeed, it has been shown that mental fatigue can increase errors during work (McCormick et al., 2012); the likelihood accidents (McCormick et al., 2012) as well as being a common symptom in patients with chronic disease (i.e. cancer patient, multiple sclerosis, depression or anxiety disorders) (Chaudhuri and Behan, 2004). It has also been demonstrated that mental fatigue can negatively affect psychomotor ability (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2005, Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005) and the capacity to tolerate continuous and prolonged exercise (van Cutsem et al., 2017). When mentally fatigued, individuals are likely to feel tired and experience a lack of energy and decreased motivation, manifesting symptoms via behavioural, physiological, and subjective changes.

Behavioural responses to mental fatigue are typically characterized by a decline in cognitive performance, usually demonstrated by an increment in errors over time and/or an increase in reaction times during standardised computer tasks (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009). Some authors have also demonstrated that mentally fatigued participants had difficulties in focusing their attention, planning, and adaptively changing strategies in the face of negative outcomes (van der Linden, Frese and Meijman, 2003, van der Linden and Eling, 2006). Other authors showed that mentally fatigued participants had difficulties in adequately preparing their responses (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2005, 2006a), and in sustaining attention and ignoring irrelevant information and confounding factors. In addition, mentally fatigued participants corrected their mistakes less often during cognitive computerized cognitive tasks and post error performance adjustments were impaired (Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005, Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2006a).

Physiological responses to mental fatigue have been linked to alterations in brain activity (Cook et al., 2007, Brownsberger et al., 2013). Recent research suggests that changes in brain electrical activity occur as a result of mental fatigue (Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005, Pires et al., 2018). Electroencephalography (EEG) was used during experiments where prolonged computerized cognitive tasks have been administered to induce mental fatigue, demonstrating an altered cortical activation (Pires et al., 2018) and resulting in the impaired functioning of the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) (Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005) and in the prefrontal cortex (Meeusen, van Cutsem and Roelands, 2021). Indeed, in these brain areas it has been hypothesised that specific neurotransmitters are involved in this phenomenon (Marcora, 2017, Meeusen, van Cutsem and Roelands, 2021). Extracellular cerebral adenosine, formed from the breakdown of adenosine triphosphate, has been found to accumulate due to the greater neural activity required by a demanding cognitive task (Marcora, 2017). This metabolite effects the whole body including the brain (Marcora, 2017) and seems to be directly involved in increasing perceived exertion (RPE) during

endurance exercise, and impairing motivation to expend effort (Martin et al., 2018). Furthermore, when adenosine antagonists (caffeine) are used, subjects can restore normal endurance performances avoiding the detrimental effect of mental fatigue (Azevedo et al., 2016). Indeed, studies involving transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS), a manipulation which increases cortical excitability of a targeted brain area with current stimulation, also appear to support this phenomenon. For example, a study of tDCS demonstrated an improvement in isometric knee-extensors time to exhaustion, improved motor drive and reduced RPE during exercise when compared to a control condition (Angius et al., 2016), supporting the idea that altered brain activity and neurotransmission can affect exercise performance and perception of effort.

When mental fatigue is present it is possible to detect changes in the three areas described previously (subjective, behavioural, and physiological), but is not necessary to detect changes in all three to experience the psychobiological state of fatigue. For example, thanks to neural compensatory mechanisms and according to the level of engagement, cognitive, performance does not necessarily decline over time, both for reaction time and accuracy of the responses during computerized prolonged cognitive tasks. . In the laboratory, to test the effect of mental fatigue on various psychomotor and exercise performances, participants are typically mentally fatigued by completing prolonged computerized tasks like the AX Continuous Performance Test (AX-CPT), Simon Task (SIMON) and the Stroop task (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Van Cutsem et al., 2017, McMorris et al., 2018, Gattoni et al., 2021). For example, during AX-CPT, a continuous stream of letters are visually presented one at a time and participants have to react when a target letter appears. During typical Stroop tasks, participants are asked to react as quickly as possible indicating the color of the word that appear on the screen. Performance on these tasks relies on the ability to sustain attention, inhibit responses, use working memory, and demonstrate cognitive flexibility (Simon, 1969, 1990, Perlstein et al., 1998, Wascher et al., 2001, Leuthold, 2011). The duration of mentally fatiguing tasks used in sports and exercise research studies range from 10 to 90 minutes, but most of the work adopting tasks lasting 30-45 minutes. A recent meta-analysis indicated that cognitive tasks that last less than 30 minutes can be as effective as more prolonged tasks but require that the participant is maximally engaged in the task (Brown et al., 2020). In order to accurately assess the time onset and level of mental fatigue that is experienced, the precise measurement of mental fatigue in performance contexts is required. Many different measures have been used to capture mental fatigue state (summarized in Table 1) including neurological measures like EEG and functional magnetic resonance imagery (fMRI), subjective measure of rating of fatigue using visual analogue scales (VAS) and questionnaires, and behavioural measures of fatigue of responses captured during cognitive tasks.

Category	Type of measure	Main investigated parameter	Mechanism related to MF	References
Physiological	EEG	Brain activity: alpha and theta power	Increase in low-frequency theta and alpha activity	Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2005; Klimesch, 1999
Physiological	fMRI	Hemodynamic response of defined brain areas	Increase in cingulate and frontal regions activity	Cook et al., 2007; Ishii, Tanaka and Watanabe, 2014
Subjective	Visual Analogue Scale (VAS)	Perception of fatigue	Increase in the perception of fatigue	Gift, 1989
Subjective	Brunell Mood Scale (BRUMS)	Different dimensions of mood	Changes in the self-reported mood	Terry, Lane and Fogarty, 2003
Subjective	NASA TLX (TLX)	Six dimensions of workload	Changes in mental workload perception	Hart and Staveland, 1988b
Behavioural	Response time	Time interval between the appearance of the stimulus and the answer provided by the participants during a demanding cognitive task	Increase in time to response to a stimulus the more the time on task	MacMahon et al., 2014; Rozand et al., 2014; Smith, Marcora and Coutts, 2015; Martin et al., 2016, Pires et al., 2018; Slimani et al., 2018; Barzegarpour et al., 2020
Behavioural	Error rate or Accuracy	Quantification of incorrect answer captured during a demanding cognitive task	Increase of errors the more the time on task	Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009; Head et al., 2016; Babu Henry Samuel et al., 2019

Table 1. Main type of measures used to detect a psychobiological state of mental fatigue

2.2. - Effects of mental fatigue on endurance performance

As described in the previous paragraphs, endurance exercise can be defined as continuous activity that last more than 120 seconds (Burnley and Jones, 2007). Endurance exercise spans a wide range of activity from light physical activity to maximal intensity exercise that can elicit the maximal oxygen uptake. Whereas endurance exercise can be assumed as a single exercise typology, different physiological limiting factors occur at different intensities (Black et al., 2017). Various studies demonstrated that mental fatigue decrease continuous and intermittent endurance performances whereas maximal effort and maximal single contraction seem not to be affected (van Cutsem et al., 2017, Brown et al., 2020). Indeed, most of the results in the literature demonstrated that continuous exercise, commonly involving continuously running and cycling experimental sessions, have demonstrated that mental fatigue impairs performances compared to non-fatigued conditions (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, MacMahon et al., 2014, Smith, Marcora and Coutts, 2015, Pires et al., 2018, Salam, Marcora and Hopker, 2018, Barzegarpour et al., 2020) despite muscle contractile function and muscle activation seeming to be to be unaffected (Pageaux et al., 2013; Rozand et al., 2014).

Contrasting findings have been reported for high intensity endurance activities, with many authors observing detrimental effects of mental fatigue on performance (Marcora, Bosio and De Morree, 2008, Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Marcora and Staiano, 2010a, Brownsberger et al., 2013, MacMahon et al., 2014, Pageaux et al., 2014, Azevedo et al., 2016, Otani et al., 2017, Penna et al., 2018, Staiano, Bosio, et al., 2019, Gattoni et al., 2021) whereas several studies have not (Martin et al., 2016, Salam, Marcora and Hopker, 2018, Silva-Cavalcante et al., 2018, Vrijkotte et al., 2018, Clark et al., 2019). Despite the equivocal results, some authors have hypothesised that exercise intensity may modulate the impairments in exercise tolerance related to mental fatigue (van Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018, Brown et al., 2020, McMorris, 2020). Indeed, two recent literature reviews have suggested that the higher the exercise intensity the lower, the impact of mental fatigue on performances (van Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018). It has been suggested that mental fatigue may disturb the decision-making process (Pageaux and Lepers, 2018) by impairing athletes' drive to exercise when intensity is lower and duration is longer, involving more 'individual thinking' in comparison to when exercise intensity is higher. When participants are mentally fatigued, the higher-than-normal perception of effort dictates early exhaustion or reduced effort over time during endurance activities. Furthermore, maintaining performance when people are mentally fatigued requires more neural activity for the same work that might not always be sustainable during long duration exercise (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2006b, Martin et al., 2018). However,

the role of mental fatigue in limiting endurance performance according at different exercise intensities remains unclear.

2.2.2 – Moderate Intensity

The effects of mental fatigue on moderate intensity exercise (which includes exercise intensities below gas exchange threshold) are under-investigated and few studies have been published on the topic. The length of time required to collect data to exhaustion and the numerous external factors that can influence results are likely to be limiting factors for these investigations. Results from the research which has been conducted, demonstrated that moderate intensity self-paced exercise in a mentally fatigued state is impaired. Indeed, Brownsberger and colleagues saw that mentally fatigued participants exercised at a lower power/velocity when they are required to cycle at a fixed perceptible intensity (11RPE) in the moderate domain (Brownsberger et al., 2013) compared to a non-fatigued condition. Similarly, Brown and Bray demonstrated that fatigued participants completed less work (energy expended in a defined amount of time) during 30 minutes of moderate cycling exercise, indicating a reduced willingness to expend energy (Brown and Bray, 2019). Interestingly, studies by Jacquet et al., and Oberste et al., (2021, 2021) used moderate exercise to counteract mental fatigue, aiming to alleviate fatigue occurrence. They found that moderate exercise led to a better recovery for mood, tiredness, self-perceived cognitive capacity, and motivation compared to the control treatment. Considering that moderate intensity exercise includes many daily activities and any movement requiring prolonged effort, it is important to understand more about how mental fatigue can influence exercise tolerance and exercise willingness in this intensity domain. Thus, further research to explore the moderator effect of mental fatigue on moderate exercise is needed.

2.2.3 – Heavy Intensity

Similarly to moderate exercise, the effect of mental fatigue on heavy intensity exercise (which includes exercise intensities between gas exchange threshold and critical power) is also under investigated. Exhaustion in the heavy domain also requires a great amount of time making it difficult to fit into a laboratory calendar, and the identification of the appropriate exercise intensity for each individual requires at least two tests (i.e. incremental exercise and a test to detect critical power). However, performance at heavy intensities is of major importance within competitive endurance sports, for example in road cycling, triathlon, long distance running (more than the half marathon) and open water swimming, where athletes engage in prolonged and hard effort. Studies that have investigated the effect of mental fatigue on heavy exercise tolerance suggested that it has a negative effect on performance. Brownsberger and colleagues found that mentally fatigued participants that

exercised at a fixed perceptive intensity (15 RPE), in the heavy domain, achieved a lower power/velocity compared to a control condition (Brownsberger et al., 2013). Mental fatigue has been shown to negatively affect performance either in cycling time trials and in time to exhaustion tests (Pires et al., 2018, Barzegarpour et al., 2020). Indeed, Barzegarpour and colleagues found that cycling time to exhaustion was largely impaired (~30%), when recreational athletes were required to exercise as much as possible in the heavy domain after the completion of a prolonged Stroop Task (Barzegarpour et al., 2020). Moreover, Pires and colleague found a significant increase in the time (2.7%) to complete 20 km cycling time trial when athletes were mentally fatigued (Pires et al., 2018). To the best of our knowledge, there has only been one field study investigating the effect of mental fatigue during a running competition (Gattoni et al., 2021). Participants in this study were divided in two different subgroups, matched for physiological parameters, and before the exercise performance one group completed 50 minutes of cognitive tasks (different response task were proposed) and the other underwent a control condition, reading newspapers. The data collected from participants during a half marathon competition showed that mental fatigue had a detrimental effect on performance (4 minutes slower), although no statistical significance was found (Cohen's $d = 0.333$; $p = 0.265$) (Gattoni et al., 2021). The authors used a between-subject randomized controlled design and due to a lack of statistical power, limited conclusions can be drawn. However, the direction of these results seems to suggest that mental fatigue has a significant negative effect on heavy exercises irrespective of the nature of the task (running, cycling, etc., or time trial or time to exhaustion). Considering that a large amount of endurance performances are carried out in at heavy intensities, very little is known about the effect of mental fatigue for these activities.

2.2.4 – Severe Intensity

Most of the research investigating the effect of mental fatigue on physical performance has involved exercise in the severe exercise domain, where exercise tolerance is attained in less than 30-45 minutes. The majority of the results published suggest that cognitive fatigue elicits a negative effect on severe intensity exercise performance but not all results are consistent (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, MacMahon et al., 2014, Pageaux et al., 2014, Azevedo et al., 2016, Martin et al., 2016, Otani et al., 2017, Filipas et al., 2018, Penna et al., 2018, Silva-Cavalcante et al., 2018, Clark et al., 2019, Staiano, Bosio, et al., 2019, Lopes et al., 2020, Schlichta et al., 2022). Dividing the results between exercise to exhaustion and time trials we can summarize the results as follows. Performance in time trials have been found to be impaired after completing prolonged cognitive tasks, in comparison to a control condition, during 1500 meters of swimming (Penna et al., 2018), 20 minutes cycling (Martin et al., 2016), 2000 meters kayaking (Staiano, Bosio, et al., 2019) and for 3 and 5

kilometers of running (MacMahon et al., 2014, Pageaux et al., 2014). Interestingly, it is possible to note that the results that reported negative effects of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance are from heterogeneous groups of participants with different fitness level (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Azevedo et al., 2016, Otani et al., 2017, Schlichta et al., 2022) and comparison between sexes display similar impairments in exercise tolerance (Lopes et al., 2020). In contrast, no detrimental effects of mental fatigue were found when a group of adolescent kayakers were required to paddle as fast as they could for 1500 meters (Filipas et al., 2018) and on cycling performances over a range of distances in trained participants (Martin et al., 2016, Silva-Cavalcante et al., 2018, Clark et al., 2019). Within the severe domain, no study has demonstrated a positive effect of mental fatigue on endurance performance, but numerous studies report no effects. It is important to note is that most of the experimental studies described here are likely to be underpowered, with a small sample size of usually less than 10 participants. Thus, some published results may be misleading, and new studies with bigger sample sizes are needed.

Taking into consideration all the results described it seems that mental fatigue, elicited by prolonged cognitive demanding tasks does affect endurance tolerance according to exercise intensity. This is in contrast with the psychobiological model of exercise tolerance and some considerations must be made. Indeed, the experimental designs used by all the previous researchers investigating mental fatigue used simple and standardizable physical tasks, leaving aside the physiological differences that are present in different exercise domains. In fact, the majority of studies that have explored the effect of mental fatigue on endurance performance used a physical task that lasted less than 30 minutes. As a consequence, the relationship between exercise tolerance and mental fatigue during actual endurance competition is unknown. On the contrary, if we focus our attention on the effects of mental fatigue on performance it seems that cognitive tasks had mainly negative effects within both moderate and heavy exercises, whereas results in the severe domain are equivocal.

Thus, we can support the hypothesis proposed by the literature that the effect of mental fatigue changes according to the exercise intensities. However, the statement that “the ergolytic effects of mental fatigue are reduced for exercises at higher intensities” needs to be supported by further investigation. Indeed, the rationale for a lower impact of mental fatigue on exercise performance at lower intensities is sound: the more time people have to counter negative thinking (as happens during lower exercise intensities) the more significant the perception of effort during exercise may be. Nevertheless, these conclusions are supported with experimental data that take into consideration supra-maximal and non-endurance exercises; whereas, focusing only on endurance exercise it is only possible to suppose a trend of the relationship between mental fatigue and exercise intensity. So, more research studies investigating the effect of mental fatigue on exercises at different intensities are needed.

Figure 1. Graphical overview of the result of the literature according to performance duration and physiological exercise domains. Data presented indicate the general results on exercise performance, the type of the physical task measured and authors. Arrows down indicate detrimental effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance according to the classical intensities domain model, based on physiological thresholds (Burnley et al., 2007). The equal symbol indicates no effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance. Arrows upward indicate a significant recovery of the perception of mental fatigue

3.0 - Aims and Objectives

As extensively discussed in the introduction chapter, exercise tolerance has been demonstrated to be limited by numerous factors, both physiological and psychological, but a wider framework including both areas is far from established. Among that limiting factors, mental fatigue seems to negatively affect the perception of effort during exercise, leading to diminished physical tolerance during endurance performances. One topical systematic review and one literature review (Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018) have hypothesised that mental fatigue affect exercise tolerance less the higher is the exercise intensity, this relationship has not been tested experimentally on different intensity domain exercises and actual results from the literature are equivocal.

In the present study we aimed to investigate the effects of mental fatigue on time to exhaustion during cycling within heavy- and severe-intensity domains by considering both the psychobiological and the physiological models of exercise tolerance. More specifically, we asked the subjects to cycle as long as possible above and below their critical power after being engaged in a prolonged cognitive demanding task or a control condition. As a secondary aim, we examined whether ergolytic effects of mental fatigue are intensity dependent.

Our hypothesis is that mental fatigue will affect heavy exercises more than severe exercises due to the extended period participants are required to overcome physical and mental fatigue and keeping themselves motivated for.

4.0 - Methodology and results

4.0.1 – Participants

Twenty-three young participants (mean \pm SD; age 26 ± 5 yr, height 177 ± 6 cm, body mass 71 ± 6 kg, 19 Male, 4 Female) volunteered to participate in this study. All participants were highly trained, competing regularly at regional and national level in road cycling and triathlon (McKay et al., 2022), and they were including high-intensity sessions and time trials in their training routine. All participants were non-smokers, normotensive, and were not using any drugs. The procedures used in this study were approved by the local ethics committee (2531CEMaugeri-27072021) and follow the ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects set by the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki. Each subject gave written informed consent before the study describing all procedures related to the study. As previously performed by our research group (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Gattoni et al., 2021), participants were naive to the real aims and hypotheses of the study, and they were told that the study aimed to investigate the effect of two different cognitive tasks on the ability to keep a defined target cadence as long as possible during subsequent cycling exercise. At the end of the final visit, participants were debriefed as to the true nature of the study.

4.0.2 – Experimental Protocol

The study used a single-blinded, randomized, counterbalanced and crossover design. Each participant visited the laboratory on five separate occasions at the same time of the day (± 2 hours) to minimize circadian variation on performance. Each session was separated by at least 72 hours. All participants completed all testing sessions within 5 weeks to minimize training or detraining effects on performance outcomes. All tests were performed with room temperature ($18\text{--}20$ °C) and air humidity ($40\text{--}60$ %) standardized. Participants were asked to avoid any caffeine-containing drinks, nicotine, and mentally demanding tasks for at least 3 hours before sessions. Moreover, they were recommended to sleep at least 7 hours per night during the period of the entire experimental protocol. Before every experimental session the compliance of the above-mentioned criteria for the optimal testing condition were verbally assessed by the authors, otherwise the session was postponed.

On the first visit, anthropometric measurements were recorded and a ramp incremental test to exhaustion on the cycle ergometer was completed, followed by a 2-minute all-out ramp sprint test (RST). In the same day, participants were also familiarized with the mental task which was planned to be used in the following sessions. From the second to the fifth sessions, participants randomly performed cycling constant work rate (CWR) exercises to the limit of tolerance: two exercises were

performed at heavy (HVY) and two exercises at severe intensity (SEV). Before CWR, participants completed two different cognitive tasks: a 45-minute Simon task (Simon), used to induce mental fatigue, or a 45-minute documentary watching (Control). The Simon task required participants to react as quickly as possible to the stimuli proposed for 3 consecutive bouts of 15 minutes. Some psychological measurements were tested by questionnaires at different timepoints: mood (MOOD) was evaluated before starting cognitive tasks; motivation (MOTIV) was assessed before cognitive tasks and CWRs; self-reported mental fatigue (VAS-M) was requested before and after cognitive tasks; subjective workload (TLX) was administered after both cognitive tasks and CWRs; and perceived Exertion (RPE) was asked during CWRs. Figure 2 shows a visual representation of the experimental procedures from second to fifth sessions.

Figure 2. Overview of the protocol of the intervention's sessions depicted on a timeline (min). *CONTROL*: 45' of video watching; *SIMON*: 45' of continuous Simon task; *HEAVY*: exercise intensity equal to 110% of critical power; *SEVERE*: exercise intensity equal 90% of critical power; *MOOD*: mood questionnaire; *MOTIV* motivational questionnaire; *VAS-M*: self-reported mental fatigue questionnaire; *TLX*: subjective workload questionnaire; *RPE*: rating of perceived exertion questionnaire.

4.0.3 - Ramp-Sprint test (RST)

The RST consisted of ramp incremental cycling exercise to exhaustion followed by a 2 min sprint test (figure 3) to detect maximal cardio-metabolic parameters and detect different exercise intensity domains (Murgatroyd et al., 2014, Goulding, Roche and Marwood, 2021). During the incremental phase, work rate started from 0 Watt (W) and was increased at 15-25 W/min according to individual fitness level. Participants were instructed to steadily increase their pedal cadence to a self- selected rate (range 75–95 rpm) and thereafter maintained it within ± 5 rpm. Exhaustion was

defined when the cadence fell from the lower bound of this range for more than 10s despite strong verbal encouragement. During the sprint phase, the cycle ergometer (LC6, Monark, Sweden) was switched from a cadence independent to a cadence-dependent (linear) mode and participants were invited to pedal as fast as possible for 2 minutes (Murgatroyd et al., 2014, Wells et al., 2014, Goulding, Roche and Marwood, 2021). The flywheel breaking force was settled to ensure an end test power around 50% between power at gas exchange threshold (W_{GET}) and peak power output (W_{peak}), measured during the ramp phase, at the preferred cadence. The average power during the last 30 seconds of the sprint phase was used to define CP (Burnley, Doust and Vanhatalo, 2006). In accordance with Murgatroyd and colleagues ((Murgatroyd et al., 2014) CP determined on the RST demonstrated a confidence interval of $-4.7 + 6.5$ W compared to a standard method described by Poole and colleagues (Poole et al., 1988).

Figure 3. Typical example of $\dot{V}O_2$, $\dot{V}CO_2$ and HR responses during RST. The graph represent the cardio-respiratory responses to ramp exercise followed by a 2-minute sprint test of a participant of the current study. $\dot{V}O_2$: red rhombus; $\dot{V}CO_2$: blue circle; HR: purple triangle, Power: brown line.

4.0.4 - Simon Task (Simon)

Participants were invited to perform a 45 minute Simon Task in front of a computer screen. The task was created and administered with an open-source online platform psytoolkit.org. The task consisted of a consecutive series of word, equal to “left” or “right”, appearing either on the right or on the left of a fixed “+”, located in the center of a computer screen (figure 4). Participants were asked

to press the button corresponding to the letter “a”, whenever the ‘left’ word appeared and to press the one corresponding to the letter “l”, whenever the ‘right’ word appeared, no matter the position of the word on the screen. The task consisted of 3 x 15-min blocks to be performed consecutively. Each block was interspersed by 30 seconds of rest. Participants were instructed to perform their best during all the trials to respond as quickly (reaction time (t_R) and accurately as possible (ER). t_R was calculated as the time between the stimuli and the response in milliseconds. ER was calculated as the percentage of errors on the total stimuli presented. To motivate participants, a financial reward of €50 was offered to the participant with the best performance. During the task, participants wore noise cancelling headphones (Bose QuietComfort 35) which produced white noise to avoid external distracting factors.

Figure 4. Typical example of the instruction for the Simon Task (top panel) and all the stimuli proposed during the task.

4.0.5 - Video watching (Control)

Control conditions consisted of watching two randomized documentary episodes, that lasted the same time required to complete SIMON (45 min). Participants were seated in front of the computer screen and wore headphones as for SIMON. Documentaries told of sports stories and were chosen in according to other authors themes were to maintain a neutral mood state (Silvestrini and Gendolla, 2007).

4.0.6 – Questionnaires

A series of questionnaires aimed to evaluate motivation, self-reported mental fatigue, mood, and subjective workload were administered through an open-source on-line platform, psytoolkit.org, at different time points as reported in figure 1. All questionnaires were presented in Italian and are available in the appendix (appendix II, II, IV and V).

4.0.6.1 – Motivation (MOTIV)

Motivation is defined as the attribute that moves us to do or not to do something (Gredler, 2001). It has been proposed that motivation influences performance and is a key factor in exercise tolerance (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b, Richter, Gendolla and Wright, 2016). Before cognitive tasks and before CWRs, intrinsic motivation and success motivation were assessed via two subscales on the motivational questionnaire (Matthews, Campbell and Falconer, 2001) that included 14 items, to be scored on a 5-point Likert scale (where 0 = not at all, 1 = a little, 2 = somewhat, 3 = very much, 4 = extremely). Example of questions are: “I would be disappointed if I failed to do well on this task”, “I wanted to succeed on the task” or “I would rather have spent the time doing the task on something else”. The total range of scores for each scale was between 0 and 28. Reliability of this scale have been demonstrated both for success motivation and intrinsic motivation subscale displaying α .87 and .81 respectively (Matthews, Campbell and Falconer, 2001).

4.0.6.2 - Self-Reported Mental Fatigue (VAS-M)

Before CWRs, a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was used to assess subjective mental fatigue (Wewers and Lowe, 1990). The VAS was a digital horizontal line divided into 20 half intervals (Gift, 1989). Participants were asked to move the cursor one of the 20-line intervals based on their actual mental fatigue state. The line ends were anchored by descriptors defining the extreme feelings of fatigue: “no fatigue at all” and “extremely fatigued”. The total range of scores was between 0 and 20. VAS scale have been demonstrated to have test-retest reliability among different field of investigation (Cella and Perry, 1986).

4.0.6.3 – Mood (MOOD)

At the beginning of each experimental session, subjective mood was evaluated by the Brunel Mood State Scale (Terry, Lane and Fogarty, 2003). Participants were invited to complete the form describing “How do you feel right now?”. The questionnaire was a shorter version of the Profile of Mood States and it consisted of 24 items (e.g. tired, anxious, nervous, confused, energetic, active) to be answered on a 5-point Likert scale (where 0 = not at all, 1 = a little, 2 = moderately, 3 = quite a bit, 4 = extremely). Items were allocated into six specific subscales: anger, confusion, depression, fatigue, tension, and vigor. Each subscale included 4 related items. The total range of scores was between 0 and 16. The questionnaire has been widely used within sports studies (Lochbaum et al.,

2021) it has satisfactory test-retest reliability, and internal consistency (Nyenhuis et al., 1999)(Nyenhuis et al. 1999).

4.0.6.4 - Subjective Workload (TLX)

The multidimensional scale NASA Task Load Index was used to estimate subjective workload that participants experienced (Hart and Staveland, 1988a). TLX completion was asked immediately after cognitive tasks and CWRs. TLX included six subscales which determine workload for different domains: Mental Demand (How much mental and perceptual activity was required?), Physical Demand (How much physical activity was required?), Temporal Demand (How much time pressure did you feel due to the rate or pace at which the task occurred?), Performance (How much successful do you think you were in accomplishing the goals of the task set by the experimenter?), Effort (How hard did you have to work to accomplish your level of performance?) and Frustration (How much irritating, annoying did you perceive the task?). Participants were asked to circle one of the 20-line intervals on each of the six scales at the point which matched their experience. Each line had two endpoint descriptors “very low” and “very high” that describe the scale. The performance-related subscale went from “good” on the left to “poor” on the right. This score was multiplied by 5, resulting in a final score between 0 and 100 for each of the subscales. TLX have been used extensively in the sport and exercise field, to measure the associated mental and physical demand (Cutsem et al., 2017, Staiano, Bosio, et al., 2019, Gattoni et al., 2021, Irvine, Jobson and Wilson, 2022) and it has also been subjected to a number of independent validations for reliability and sensitivity (Hart, 2006).

4.0.6.5 - Perceived Exertion (RPE)

During CWRs, participants were asked to indicate their perceived effort at random time-points, chosen by the authors, to avoid a temporal anchor and preventing them from having a reference to improve performance when they repeated the test. Perceived effort is the conscious sensation of how hard, heavy, and strenuous a physical task is (Marcora, 2010). The rating of perceived exertion scale (Borg, 1982) (RPE) measured the intensity of perceived exertion on a 15-point category scale representing equal intervals and ranging from 6 (“no exertion at all”) to 20 (“maximal exertion”). Seven of the 13 intermediate points were anchored to verbal expressions of effort such as “very light,” “somewhat hard,” and “heavy”. RPE scale was set in front of the ergometer and height-adjusted to ensure that each subject could easily indicate the value associated with their perception. RPE scale has been demonstrated to be reliable to detect changes in perception of effort in different sports (Borg, 1962, 1982).

4.0.7 - Time to exhaustion test (TTE)

CWR tests were performed as soon as possible after SIMON and CONTROL and were preceded by 5 min of warm-up at 1.5 W/Kg. CWRs intensity was randomly chosen between heavy (CWR_{HVY}) and severe (CWR_{SEV}) domains, corresponding to a work rate equal to CP -10% and CP +10%, respectively. During CWRs, participants were instructed to cycle for as long as possible by keeping cadence close to the target cadence defined during the RST. Time to exhaustion (TTE) was defined when participants were unable to keep the preferred cadence in the range desired (with a margin of plus or minus two revolution per minute) after three consecutive warnings in the same minute. External factors during the experimental sessions were restricted to avoid any potential confounding effect of factors other than the cognitive tasks including motivational stimuli, no speaking or the presence of different staff during the experimental session.

4.0.8 - Physiological measurements during TTE

During RST and CWRs, pulmonary ventilation ($\dot{V}E$), oxygen consumption ($\dot{V}O_2$) and CO_2 output ($\dot{V}CO_2$) were determined breath-by-breath by a metabolic cart (Vyntus CPX, CareFusion, Germany). Before each test, gas analyzers were calibrated with ambient air and a gas mixture of known concentration (O_2 : 16%, CO_2 : 4%) and the turbine flowmeter was calibrated with a 3-L syringe at three different flow rates. Breath frequency was defined as number of breaths in one minute (B_f). RER was calculated as $\dot{V}O_2/\dot{V}CO_2$. GET was determined from pulmonary gas exchange data of the ramp phase of the RST using the “V-slope” method and “secondary criteria” (Beaver, Wasserman and Whipp, 1986). Heart rate (HR) was monitored continuously during all the exercises using a chest band (Garmin HMR-DUAL, KA, USA). Peak values ($\dot{V}O_2$, $\dot{V}CO_2$, $\dot{V}E$, B_f and HR) were determined as the highest 20 s average value over the last minutes of exercise. At rest and at discrete time points (1, 3, and 5 minutes) in the recovery, 20 μ L of capillary blood was obtained from a preheated earlobe. The determination of blood lactate concentration ($[La]_b$) was assessed by an enzymatic method. The analyzer (Biosen C-line, EKF, Germany) was calibrated before each measurement with a standard solution containing 12 mmol/L of lactate. $[La]_b$ peak values were determined as the highest value in the recovery.

$\dot{V}O_2$ kinetics during TTE were mathematically evaluated during transitions from warm-up phase (at 1.5 W/Kg) to heavy or severe intensity exercises. Breath-by-breath $\dot{V}O_2$ values obtained during exercise were averaged every 10 s and then data were fitted by defined equations (figure 5). To evaluate the presence of a slow component (Porcelli et al., 2012), data were fitted by the function:

$$y(t) = y_{BAS} + A_f[1 - e^{-(t-TD_f)/\tau_f}] + A_s[1 - e^{-(t-TD_s)/\tau_s}] \text{ (equation 1)}$$

where t is time, y_{BAS} indicates the baseline $\dot{V}O_2$, A_f is the amplitude between the y_{BAS} and the steady state $\dot{V}O_2$ during the fundamental component, TD_f is the time delay, τ_f the time constant of the function for the fundamental component.

The slow component, however, did not always follow an exponential function, being sometimes linearly related to the time of exercise. In these cases, a second equation (equation 2) was also used, with an exponential function for the fundamental component and a linear function for the slow component (exponential + linear fitting) (Porcelli et al., 2012) :

$$y(t) = y_{BAS} + A_f[1 - e^{-(t-TD_f)/\tau_f}] + S[t - TD_s] \text{ (equation 2)}$$

where S (slope) is the angular coefficient of the linear regression of $\dot{V}O_2$ versus time t . The best fit of the data between the two models was determined using the F-test.

Figure 5. Representation of the $\dot{V}O_2$ responses during Time To Exhaustion exercises of a participant of the current study. Breath by breath data were averaged every 10 s and then were fitted by defined equations to understand the nature of the slow component.

4.0.9 - Statistical analysis

A priori sample size calculation was performed to ensure a statistical power of 0.80 using G*Power 3.1. Calculation based on the performance loss data obtained from the meta-analysis of Holgado et colleague (2020) (mean effect size -0.51) displayed that a sample size of 20 participants

was adequately powered. Taking into consideration potential dropouts (30%) we recruited 26 participants.

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD, except as otherwise specified. The data were tested for normality using a Shapiro-Wilk W-test. Repeated-measure one-way ANOVA was used to test the effect of time on reaction time (t_r) and error rate (ER). Repeated-measures one-way ANOVA was used to detect changes between the four sessions (CONTROL 1 vs CONTROL 2; SIMON 1 vs SIMON 2) for each item of MOTIV, MOOD and TLX. Repeated-measures two-way ANOVA with time (BEFORE vs AFTER) and interventions (CONTROL 1 vs CONTROL 2 vs SIMON 1 vs SIMON 2) as within subject factors was used to evaluate changes in VAS-M. Sphericity was checked using Mauchly's test. For all parameters, sphericity was verified by Mauchly's test and Geisser-Greenhouse correction was performed when the assumption of sphericity had been violated. When significant main effects or interactions were observed, Bonferroni's test was used for post-hoc analysis.

Based on the assumption that TTE between exercise domain is theoretically significant, we tested the effect of SIMON on the TTE, within domain, with a two-tailed paired t-test, for both HVY and SEV domain. Comparison between domain loss was checked using a two-tailed paired t-test on the percentage of performance loss between CONTROL and SIMON. Physiological responses to exercise and RPE slope within each domain were tested with a two-tailed paired t-test. Data fitting by linear or exponential functions was performed by the least-squared residuals method. Fitting comparisons with different models were carried out using the F-test. The level of significance was set at $p > 0.05$. All statistical procedures were completed using Prism 8.0 (GraphPad Software, CA, USA).

4.2 – Results

Peak data for the main **physiological variables** obtained during the incremental phase of RST are reported in Table 1. $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ was $53.5 \pm 8.0 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and it was not different from $\dot{V}O_2$ obtained during the sprint phase (3.744 ± 0.731 and $53.7 \pm 8.5 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, $p > 0.377$). At the end of test, HR was $95.6 \pm 3.3 \%$ of age-predicted value, $[\text{La}]_b$ was $9.7 \pm 1.6 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and RPE was 18.9 ± 0.4 . CP determined during the 2 minutes all-out phase was $279 \pm 58 \text{ W}$, corresponding to $75 \pm 4 \%$ of W_{peak} .

W	$\dot{V}O_2$	$\dot{V}CO_2$	RER	$\dot{V}E$	B_f	V_t	HR
watt	$L\text{min}^{-1}$	$L\text{min}^{-1}$	-	$L\text{min}^{-1}$	$b\text{min}^{-1}$	L	$b\text{min}^{-1}$
368 ± 65	3.783 ± 0.736	4.778 ± 0.894	1.27 ± 0.05	173 ± 33	62 ± 10	2.31 ± 0.38	184 ± 8

Table 2. cardio-metabolic end-exercise values determined during RST. Mean values \pm SD. W , power; $\dot{V}O_2$, oxygen uptake; $\dot{V}CO_2$, carbon dioxide output; RER, respiratory exchange ratio; $\dot{V}E$, pulmonary ventilation; B_f , Breath frequency; V_t , tidal volume; HR, heart rate; W_{GET} , gas exchange threshold power; $\dot{V}O_{2\text{GET}}$, oxygen uptake at the gas exchange threshold.

t_r and ER data are shown in Figure 6. Although t_r was 2.3 ± 9.3 % lower at 45 min compared to 15 min, t_r did not change significantly during the protocol ($F_{(1.3, 27.7)} = 1.28$, $p = 0.278$) (Figure 6A). ER showed a significant main effect of time ($F_{(1.5, 33.4)} = 19.8$, $p < 0.001$). ER significantly increased from 15 to 30 min ($p = 0.011$) and from 30 min to 45 min ($p < 0.001$), resulting 1.4 ± 1.4 % higher at 45 min compared to 15 min (Figure 6B).

Figure 6. Mean time-course changes in reaction time, t_r , and error rate, ER, during the consecutive bout of SIMON task. Mean \pm SEM data for reaction time (t_r ; panel A; black rhombus) and error rate (ER; panel B; White rhombus) for each consecutive bout of 15 minutes during Simon task. # significantly different from 15'; \$ significantly different from 30'.

In **MOOD** (Figure 7), no session effect was shown for Anger ($F_{(2.71, 59.66)} = 0.448, p = 0.700$) and Confusion ($F_{(2.59, 56.94)} = 1.017, p = 0.384$) and Depression ($F_{(2.69, 59.10)} = 2.382, p = 0.085$) and Fatigue ($F_{(2.23, 49.07)} = 0.258, p = 0.797$) and Tension ($F_{(2.34, 51.54)} = 1.637, p = 0.201$) as well as for Vigor ($F_{(2.58, 56.75)} = 0.389, p = 0.731$).

Figure 7. Mean MOOD state before every experimental session. Mean \pm SD data for every item of the MOOD questionnaire collected at the beginning of each experimental session (four sessions: CONTROL 1 and 2; SIMON 1 and 2).

In **MOTIV** (Figure 8), no session effect was shown for intrinsic motivation before both cognitive tasks ($F_{(2.15, 47.35)} = 0.195, p = 0.839$) and CWRs ($F_{(2.70, 56.75)} = 2.483, p = 0.076$). Similar results were observed for success motivation before both cognitive tasks ($F_{(2.75, 60.48)} = 1.729, p = 0.175$) and CWRs ($F_{(2.60, 57.26)} = 0.409, p = 0.719$).

Figure 8. Mean intrinsic and success motivation for the subsequent cognitive and physical tasks. Mean \pm SD data for motivation (MOTIV) questionnaire collected in each experimental session (four sessions: CONTROL 1 and 2; SIMON 1 and 2) before cognitive tasks and before CWRs.

From TLX (Figure 9), there were significant differences for every factor across sessions (Mental demand: $F(2.22, 48.86) = 53.57, p < 0.001$; Physical demand: $F(2.33, 51.31) = 5.11, p = 0.007$; Temporal demand: $F(2.45, 53.936) = 27.54, p < 0.001$; Performance: $F(2.73, 60.03) = 2.86, p = 0.049$; Effort; $F(2.58, 56.81) = 70.01, p < 0.001$; Frustration: $F(2.61, 57.35) = 30.19, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis demonstrated no differences between exercise intensities; CONTROL 1 and CONTROL 2, as well as between SIMON 1 and SIMON 2. There were, however, significant differences between CONTROL AND SIMON conditions with the CONTROL conditions being significantly lower in mental and temporal demand, effort and frustration (all $p < 0.001$). On the contrary, there were no significant differences in perceived performance and physical demand between CONTROL and SIMON conditions.

Figure 9. Effect of mentally fatiguing task on subjective perception of workload. Effect of mentally fatiguing task (CONTROL 1 and 2; SIMON 1 and 2) on subjective workload, for each item of the NASA-TLX questionnaire, in arbitrary units (AU). Data are displayed as mean \pm SD. * statistical significance from post-hoc analysis.

VAS-M (figure 10) shows time ($F_{(1.0, 21.0)} = 21.00, p < 0.001$) and interventions ($F_{(2.8, 59.1)} = 4.674, p = 0.006$) effects and a time x intervention interaction ($F_{(2.47, 51.92)} = 15.73, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis demonstrates a significant increase in VAS-M across the cognitive task only in the SIMON 1 ($p < 0.001$) and SIMON 2 ($p < 0.001$). Indeed VAS-M changed: from 7.6 to 8.21 in CONTROL 1, from 7.34 to 8.38 in CONTROL 2, from 7.59 to 13.11 in SIMON 1 and from 6.66 to 13.27 in SIMON 2, before cognitive tasks and before CWRs respectively.

Figure 10. Effect of cognitive tasks on subjective ratings of mental fatigue (VAS-M). Data are expressed in arbitrary units (AU) and are displayed as mean \pm SD. * statistical significance from post-hoc analysis

Power output of the CWRs was 253 ± 54 W and 304 ± 62 W in CWR_{HVY} and CWR_{SEV}, respectively. During both CWR_{HVY} and CWR_{SEV}, **physiological data** were not significantly different between SIMON and CONTROL (Table 2). At the end of CWR_{HVY}, $\dot{V}O_2$ was 89 ± 5 % and 87 ± 6 % of $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ for CONTROL and SIMON, respectively. At the end of CWR_{SEV}, $\dot{V}O_2$ was 97 ± 9 % and 95 ± 10 % of $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ for CONTROL and SIMON, respectively. RPE was not significantly different between SIMON and CONTROL at the end of CWR_{HVY} (18.8 ± 1.4 and 19.0 ± 2.3 , respectively; $p > 0.05$) and CWR_{SEV} (19.2 ± 1.1 and 19.2 ± 1.0 for SIMON and CONTROL, respectively; $p > 0.05$). The slope (RPE_{slope}) of the linear relationship between RPE and time was significantly higher in SIMON (CWR_{HVY}: 0.140 ± 0.001 $1 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$; CWR_{SEV}: 0.971 ± 0.010 $1 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) compared to CONTROL (CWR_{HVY}: 0.120 ± 0.001 $1 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, $p < 0.001$; CWR_{SEV}: 0.857 ± 0.008 $1 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, $p < 0.001$).

		HEAVY		SEVERE	
		CONTROL	SIMON	CONTROL	SIMON
$\dot{V}O_2$	$L \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$	3.362 ± 0.671	3.280 ± 0.612	3.646 ± 0.654	3.550 ± 0.629
$\dot{V}CO_2$	$L \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$	3.333 ± 0.687	3.297 ± 0.685	4.250 ± 0.791	4.188 ± 0.802
RER	-	0.99 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.05	1.16 ± 0.10	1.18 ± 0.11
$\dot{V}E$	$L \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$	122 ± 28	121 ± 31	153 ± 29	151 ± 30
B_f	$b \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$	51 ± 10	51 ± 10	55 ± 8	55 ± 11
HR	$b \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$	172 ± 9	172 ± 10	175 ± 7	172 ± 8
$[La]_b$	$mmol \cdot L^{-1}$	6.08 ± 2.68	5.87 ± 2.07	9.64 ± 2.47	8.86 ± 1.95

Table 3. Main cardio-metabolic end-exercise values determined during constant work rate exercises. *Mean values \pm SD. $\dot{V}O_2$, oxygen uptake; $\dot{V}CO_2$, carbon dioxide output; $\dot{V}E$, pulmonary ventilation; B_f , Breath frequency; HR, heart rate; $[la]_b$ capillary blood lactate concentration.*

Figure 11 shows **time course of $\dot{V}O_2$** obtained by all the participants during CWR_{HVY} and CWR_{SEV} after both SIMON and CONTROL. $\dot{V}O_2$ kinetics were described by equation 1 for 22 out of 23 participants in CWR_{HVY} and by equation 2 for all participants in CWR_{SEV} . τ_f ranged from 37.4 to 42.2 s and no differences were observed between domains and conditions (all $P>0.05$). During CWR_{HVY} , A_f was 1.376 ± 0.476 and 1.333 ± 0.447 $L\cdot min^{-1}$ respectively for CONTROL and SIMON. During CWR_{SEV} , A_f was 1.622 ± 0.559 and 1.575 ± 0.471 $L\cdot min^{-1}$ in CONTROL and SIMON, respectively. A_s ranged from 0.237 to 0.283 $L\cdot min^{-1}$, resulting in a slow component of about 15% of total amplitude for all conditions.

TTE was significantly reduced after SIMON, compared to CONTROL in both exercise intensity domains ($p=0.03$ and $p=0.02$ for CWR_{HVY} and CWR_{SEV} , respectively) as described in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Pulmonary O_2 uptake ($\dot{V}O_2$) during constant work rate (CWR) exercise at HEAVY and SEVERE exercise intensity. Each data point indicates the mean breath-by-breath values averaged every 10 s of all participants. Data are displayed as mean \pm SEM. * TTE significantly different between SIMON and CONTROL within exercise domain. Gray circle: CONTROL HEAVY; Black circle: SIMON HEAVY; Gray triangle: CONTROL SEVERE; Black triangle: SIMON SEVERE.

Performance changes between CONTROL and SIMON ranged from -51.4 % to +44.8 % in CWR_{HVY} and from -45.5 % to +51.7 % in CWR_{SEV} (Figure 12), resulting in a performance loss which was **not significantly different between domains** ($p = 0.853$) and resulting in a decrement of about -10.7 % for the CWR_{HVY} and 8.2 % for the CWR_{SEV} .

Figure 12. Effect of mental fatigue on performance loss within HEAVY and SEVERE exercise domains. The gray bars indicate the SIMON performances reported as percentage of the CONTROL conditions, for the HEAVY (SIMON_{HVY}, top bar) and SEVERE (SIMON_{SEV}, bottom bar) exercise domain. Data are displayed as mean \pm SEM. Black circle represent individual values.

5.0 – Discussion

In the present study we tested the effect of a demanding cognitive task on TTE cycling performance during heavy- and severe-intensity exercises, examining whether the ergolytic effects of mental fatigue are intensity dependent. Results indicate that participating in 45 minutes of a Simon task induced mental fatigue, increased perception of effort and reduced exercise tolerance in both heavy and severe domains in comparison to a control condition, although all subjects were adequately motivated in performing the maximal effort. The impairment in cycling performance was not associated with changes in any of the physiological variables investigated. Interestingly, and contrary to our hypothesis, we did not find differences in performance loss between domains. Thus, the current data suggests that exercise intensity does not seem to moderate the impact of mental fatigue on endurance performance.

Mental fatigue. In the present work, we tested the effects of mental fatigue on endurance exercise performance. One key aspect of the study was to induce mental fatigue in our subjects before the exercise and we administered a Simon task of 45 min for this purpose (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2006b). To verify the presence of mental fatigue we tested cognitive performance and collected responses to questionnaires related to subjective feelings of mental fatigue. Reaction time or accuracy during the demanding cognitive task were used to investigate behavioural changes (Lorist et al., 2000). During Simon tasks, participants showed a negative trend in error rate, although no significant changes occurred in reaction time (Fig. 5). Various studies have shown negative trends in both reaction time (Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005, Smith, Marcora and Coutts, 2015) and an increase in number of errors (Lorist et al., 2000) as a function of time-on-task when subjects experience mental fatigue. The experience of mental fatigue during the current study can also be assessed via the participants' subjective perceptions via validated questionnaires (Hart and Staveland, 1988b, Gift, 1989, Borg, 1998, Matthews, Campbell and Falconer, 2001). Indeed, engagement in 45 minutes of cognitive task significantly increased participant's feeling of mental fatigue and perception of workload compared to the control task. These results mirror previous findings using similar cognitive tasks (Brownsberger et al., 2013, Martin et al., 2016, Pires et al., 2018, Slimani et al., 2018, MacMahon, Hawkins and Schücker, 2019, Barzegarpour et al., 2020). In addition, many works have previously described that mental fatigue increases the perception of effort during exercise (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, van Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018, Brown et al., 2020). Our subjects demonstrated a steeper increase of the perception of effort over time both for heavy and severe exercises. We observed changes in behavioural and subjective data, and we can summarize that mental fatigue was successfully induced by our protocol.

Effects of mental fatigue on heavy and severe exercises. After inducing mental fatigue, we investigated the main aim of our study by evaluating endurance exercise performance after the Simon task and control condition within different exercise intensities. We tested time to exhaustion and physiological responses to exercise in two different domains: heavy (10% below critical power) and severe (10% above critical power) in agreement with the classical physiological model (Poole et al., 2020). In the heavy intensity domain, subjects cycled for about 35 minutes whereas in the severe intensity domain they exercised for about 10 minutes and physical performance deteriorated significantly when mental fatigue was present in both domains. These different time to exhaustion conditions were associated with different physiological responses, with cardio-metabolic end-exercise values being lower in the heavy domain than in the severe one (Table 2). This is not surprising if we consider that exercise interruption is determined by an incapacity of the fatigued neuromuscular system to produce the speed/power required by the task, despite maximal voluntary effort (Gandevia, 2001) and this phenomenon is intensity-domain specific (Black et al., 2017). Without considering moderate (below the lactate threshold) exercise, it has been demonstrated that exhaustion is related to the depletion of muscle glycogen and the disturbance of muscle milieu (low [PCr] and pH, ...) in the heavy domain (Black et al., 2017). On the other hand, severe-intensity exercise (in)tolerance is associated with progressive degeneration of muscle milieu, that develop more rapidly the higher the power output is above CP, and it causes peripheral fatigue and early exercise cessation.

In the present study, the exercise tolerance in the heavy domain was significantly lower following the completion of a cognitive task in comparison to the control condition (approximately 10% lower, see figure 11) As for exercise in the severe domain results were similar whereby time to exhaustion was significantly lower after the Simon task, compared to the control task (8.2%, figure 11 and 12). The current results are in line with some of the previous studies which have investigated the effect of mental fatigue in the heavy domain. Indeed, Pires et colleagues (Pires et al., 2018) showed mentally fatigued subjects needed more time to complete 20km cycling distance. Similarly, Barzegarpour and colleagues (Barzegarpour et al., 2020) found a substantial performance impairment when cognitive task was carried out during cycling time to exhaustion at 65% of maximal work-rate. Finally, Brownsberger et al., (2013) found a reduction of approximately 8% in power mean output when mentally fatigued participants were asked to cycle at a fixed perception of effort, which is attributable at the heavy domain (15 RPE).

There are contrasting results in the literature for the Severe intensity domain. Some authors found significant impairments in performance when participants were asked to complete a defined short distance at very high intensity after a mentally fatiguing task (MacMahon et al., 2014, Pageaux

et al., 2014, Martin et al., 2016, Penna et al., 2018, Staiano et al., 2018) whereas other authors have not found such impairments in performance as a result of mental fatigue (Martin et al., 2016, Filipas et al., 2018, Silva-Cavalcante et al., 2018, Clark et al., 2019). On the contrary, and in agreement with our results, all the previous studies that have investigated the effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance in the severe domain using time to exhaustion tests found significant impairments in performance as a result of mental fatigue induced by a cognitive task (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Pageaux, Marcora and Lepers, 2013, Azevedo et al., 2016, Otani et al., 2017, Salam, Marcora and Hopker, 2018, Lopes et al., 2020, Schlichta et al., 2022).

Interestingly, in the current study the impairments in time to exhaustion in heavy and severe domains were not related to cardiometabolic responses to exercise at exhaustion, which did not differ from control condition (table 2). Similarly, $\dot{V}O_2$ kinetic parameters were not affected by the mental fatigue condition. Previous studies had already demonstrated this phenomenon, that mental fatigue had no influence on metabolic parameters (Marcora, Staiano and Manning, 2009, Pageaux, Marcora and Lepers, 2013, Pageaux et al., 2015, van Cutsem et al., 2017). However, the present results extend previous finding to physiological responses within a specific intensity domain, reinforcing the concept that mental fatigue operates via specific psychobiological mechanisms which should be taken into account when exercise tolerance is evaluated. Indeed, Marcora et colleagues (Marcora, 2010, Marcora and Staiano, 2010b, Pageaux, 2014) demonstrated that exhausted subjects are typically able to exercise maximally for a few seconds at a power significantly higher than the power required by the task. Moreover, subsequent studies have demonstrated that time to exhaustion during endurance exercise is also determined by two psychological constructs: perception of effort and potential motivation (Marcora and Staiano, 2010b). More specifically, physical efforts are interrupted when the perception of effort reach the maximal point that which the participant wishes to exert. Thus, it is likely that early exhaustion can be justified by a steeper increase in perception of effort or changes in motivation (Marcora and Staiano, 2010b, Pageaux, 2014, Staiano et al., 2018). The interplay between mental fatigue and exercise tolerance is the classical example of the importance of psychobiological variables in the impairment of the endurance performance.

Interestingly, when we compared performance loss in the two domains, we did not find differences in time to exhaustion impairments between heavy and severe as we had hypothesised. This is somewhat surprising if we consider that previous reviews about mental fatigue suggested an inverse relation between exercise intensity and ergolytic effects of mental fatigue (van Cutsem et al., 2017, McMorris et al., 2018, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018, Brown et al., 2020). More specifically, they examined carryover effects of mental fatigue on different types of physical tasks (e.g., aerobic,

resistance, maximal anaerobic, motor skills) and concluded “the higher the exercise intensity the lower the impact of mental fatigue” (van Cutsem et al., 2017, Pageaux and Lepers, 2018).

Why were the authors led to this conclusion? One hypothesis could be that, since mental fatigue has negative effect on perception of effort (Pageaux and Lepers, 2018), mentally fatigued subjects could demonstrate higher performance loss when they have to exercise at a lower intensity (and for a longer time) than those who have to exercise at a higher intensity exercise (and shorter time) due to the bigger extent of time people have to face in order not to give up. Similarly, negative changes in motivation should lead to same hypothetical results. However, in our study this was not the case. Indeed, at the beginning of each experimental session participants were in the same mood state and they were equally motivated and no changes in intrinsic and success motivation between conditions were observed both before mental tasks and exercises (specifying, after the mental task) (figure 8). Therefore, we can assume that participant’s daily habits remained the same in every experimental session, and motivation was unaffected by cognitive demanding tasks, excluding mood and motivation as confounding parameters in determining performance outcome, with mental fatigue not important for motivation towards the upcoming task (McCormick, Meijen and Marcora, 2015). In addition, as already demonstrated, participants demonstrated lower slopes of perception of effort over time in the control conditions compared to the fatiguing conditions, in both domains despite similar end-exercise perception of effort but performance loss was not different between exercise intensities.

In contrast with the general hypothesis, one possible explanation of the result presented could be that the effect of mental fatigue could directly affect exercise tolerance, rather than changes in motivation, as there were no differences in the psychological measures. Indeed, in accordance with the psychobiological model of exercise tolerance, changes in motivation or in the perception of effort could lead to changes in performance outcome. In our case, we can suppose that prolonged mentally demanding tasks, which lead to participants being mentally fatigued, negatively affected the perception of effort and consequently the capacity to continue exercising.

6.0 Strengths and Limitations

When we consider the physiological model, we distinguish three exercise domains: moderate, heavy, and severe. In this study we tested the ergolytic effects of mental fatigue on heavy and severe domains, without considering the moderate domain. We selected the heavy and severe exercise domains as most sporting events are usually performed in these domains, above lactate threshold (Poole et al., 2020). Moreover, time to task failure, could be infinite within moderate domain and thus testing the effects of mental fatigue at this exercise intensity would have required a very complex setup and a long-time availability by the participants. Nevertheless, it would add valuable insights if

researchers could overcome the practical issues and investigate potential different effects of mental fatigue on exercise performance in the moderate intensity domain. Finally, in the current work we measured psycho-physiological parameters, but some results demonstrated that brain electrical activity and neurotransmission are involved in the ergolytic effects of mental fatigue (Boksem, Meijman and Lorist, 2005, Lorist, Boksem and Ridderinkhof, 2005, Roelands et al., 2008, Lorist et al., 2009, Marcora, 2017, Meeusen, van Cutsem and Roelands, 2021). Future research studies should evaluate to investigate neurocognitive factors mechanistic involved in mental fatigue to better elucidate potential mechanistic bases for the influence of mental fatigue on endurance performance.

Lastly, the use of standardized cognitive task helped us, and most of the cited authors investigating the effect of mental fatigue, to define the amount of mental workload participant have made. Unfortunately, these tasks are unrealistic from a real-life point of view and future works should use more applied tasks, such as social media use, sending emails, workplace tasks and homework to understand the real effects of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance.

7.0 Practical Implications

Since the result here presented display a significative effect of mental fatigue on exercise tolerance during endurance exercise - when exercise intensity is above and below critical power - it may be prudent for athletes to avoid any mentally fatiguing tasks before competitions and training. Indeed, for anyone that is planning to make exercise continuously it is worth to understand that not only physical fatigue dictate how long you keep exercising at a fixed intensity, but psychological determinants must be integrated. That approach must be known and used by both athletes and coaches that aim to maximize performance.

Conversely, in the case that is not possible to avoid psychological stressor, like media interview, long travel, sport-related stressor, etcetera, it is worth thinking to implement training session about “mental fatigue tolerance”. Indeed, there beings to be an expanding literature about the possible capacity to reduce the effect of mental fatigue using a pre-planned cognitive-stressor bouts during physical training (Staiano, Merlini, et al., 2019).

Both these approaches could help athletes, trainers, and amateurs to better overcome potential negative effects of mental fatigue.

8.0 Conclusion

In summary, this experimental investigation shows that prolonged and demanding cognitive activity which impairs performance during a subsequent cycling endurance exercise both above and below the critical power. Comparison of mental fatigue-related performance losses between heavy and severe exercise revealed no difference in the ergolytic effects of mental fatigue on exercise domains. According to the psychobiological model of exercise tolerance, perception of effort is the most likely mediator of the negative effect of mental fatigue on endurance performance. Further studies are required to investigate the neurophysiological alterations associated with mental fatigue in lower intensity endurance exercise and ‘in field’ settings.

On a more practical perspective, the present study suggests that high intensity endurance exercise can be negatively affected by mental fatigue irrespective of the exercise intensities above or below critical power (or critical speed / lactate turning point).

9.0 References

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10.0 Appendix

Appendix I: data table reporting the results from the literature about the effects of mental fatigue on endurance exercise tolerance, according to the different exercises intensity domains.

1ST AUTHOR	YEAR	SUBJECTS	AGE	PHYSICAL LEV.	COGNITIVE INTERVENTION		EXERCISE	EXERCISE INTENSITY	RESULTS	
					Type and Duration				Cognitive task	exercise performance
<i>only first</i>	<i>year</i>	<i>n°</i>	<i>mean±SD</i>	<i>mean±SD</i>	-	<i>min</i>	-	-	-	-
Brownsberger	2013	8 M 4 F	24 ± 5	56±6	Task vigilance	90	Self paced cycling (RPE 11)	MOD	NA	↓ self-selected power
Jacquet	2021	7 M 30 F	20.6 ± 0.7	NA	TLDDB task	32	15 min of moderate activity	MOD	NA	↑ Recovery on the subjective mental fatigue
Oberste	2021	47 M 52 F	21.6 ± 3.6	NA	Trail Making Test	60	30 min moderate	MOD	↓ cognitive performance	↑ Recovery on the subjective mental fatigue
Brown	2019	13 M 12 F	22.8 ± 3.5	Active	Stroop test	50	30 minutes Self paced cycling	MOD	NA	↓ total work
Pires	2018	8 M	29.3 ± 7.9	64.1 ± 4.8	Rapid Visual Information Processing Test	30	20 km cycling time trial	HVY	↑ error = reaction time	↓ 2.7% TT in MF
Barzegarpour	2022	10 M	21 ± 3	recreational cyclists	modified Stroop task	45	CWR TTE @65% PPO	HVY	↑ reaction time	↓ ~27-30% TTE in MF
Brownsberger	2013	8 M 4 F	24 ± 5	56±6	Task vigilance simple and search response tasks	90	Self paced cycling (RPE 15)	HVY	NA	↓ self-selected power
Gattoni	2021	46 M	43.8 ± 8.6	46.0 ± 4.1	Stroop Color-Word Test	50	half marathon TT	HVY	NA	↓ performance (4 min slower)
Penna	2018	16 M	15.5 ± 0.5	trained swimmers	Stroop Color-Word Test	30	1500 m TT swimming	SEV	NA	↓ performance (-1.2%)
Filipas	2018	17 M 6 F	11 ± 1.06	active	Stroop test	60	1500 m TT kayak	SEV	NA	= performance = pacing
Martin	2016	11 M	23.4 ± 6.4	professional cyclist	Stroop Color-Word Test	30	20 min TT cycling	SEV	↑ reaction time	= performance
Martin	2016	9 M	25.6 ± 5.3	recreational cyclists	Stroop Color-Word Test	30	20 min TT cycling	SEV	↑ reaction time	↓ performance (-4.4%)
Staiano	2019	13 M	16.4 ± 0.8	national kayakers	Stroop Color-Word Test	60	2000 m TT kayak	SEV	NA	↓ performance (-5.4%) ↓ power output ↓ stroke rate
MacMahon	2014	18 M 2 F	25.4 ± 3.2	trained	AX-CPT	90	3000 m TT running	SEV	= reaction time = error	↓ performance (-1.7%)
Silva-Cavalcante	2018	8 M	53.6 ± 5.9	recreational cyclists	AX-CPT	90	4 km TT cycling	SEV	NA	= performance
Pageaux	2014	8M 4F	21 ± 1	trained	Modified Stroop Color-Word Test	30	5 km TT running	SEV	= reaction time = error	↓ performance (-5.3%) = pacing strategy
Clark	2019	10 M 10M	27.4 ± 6.3	58.3 ± 4.1 39.0 ± 7.3	Stroop Color-Word Test	20	6 min TT cycling	SEV	= reaction time = error	= performance
Azevedo	2016	24 M	24 ± 2	45.2 ± 3	AX-CPT	90	80% PPO TTE cycling	SEV	NA	↓ performance (= -6%) Caffeine counteract MF
Marcora	2009	10 M 6 F	26 ± 3	52 ± 8	AX-CPT	90	80% PPO TTE cycling	SEV	NA	↓ performance (-13.4%)
Otani	2017	8 M	22.0 ± 0.6	45.2 ± 6.0	Stroop test	90	80% V'O2max TTE cycling	SEV	NA	↓ performance
Lopes	2020	18 M 17 F	25.0 ± 1.0 25.0 ± 1.0	53.7 ± 1.0 48.6 ± 0.8	Stroop test	45	90% VeelPeak TTE running	SEV	NA	↓ performance Male ↓ performance Female No sex differences
Salam	2018	11 M	38 ± 6	60.5 ± 4.1	Stroop test	30	3-5 CWR TTE to detect Critical	SEV	NA	= estimation of Critical Power ↓ estimation of W'
Schlichta	2022	12	25.1 ± 5.3	NA	Stroop test	30	80% PPO TTE cycling	SEV	NA	↓ performance (-29%)

Appendix II: Italian version of the MOOD questionnaire administered during the experimental sessions

THE BRUNEL MOOD SCALE (BRUMS)

Di seguito vengono riportati alcuni aggettivi utilizzati per descrivere il proprio stato dell'umore. Leggi ciascun aggettivo con attenzione e cerchi la risposta che meglio descrive:

COME TI SENTI ADESSO, IN QUESTO MOMENTO.

UTILIZZA LA SCALA DA 0 A 4 DESCRITTA QUI SOTTO.

0 = per niente 1 = un po' 2 = abbastanza 3 = molto 4 = moltissimo

Item	0	1	2	3	4
1. Spaventato	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Vivace	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Confuso	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Esausto	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Depresso	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Scoraggiato	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Seccato	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Esaurito	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Scombussolato	<input type="radio"/>				
10. Indolente	<input type="radio"/>				
11. Amareggiato	<input type="radio"/>				
12. Infelice	<input type="radio"/>				
13. Ansioso	<input type="radio"/>				
14. Preoccupato	<input type="radio"/>				
15. Energico	<input type="radio"/>				
16. Triste	<input type="radio"/>				
17. Intontito	<input type="radio"/>				
18. Nervoso	<input type="radio"/>				
19. Arrabbiato	<input type="radio"/>				
20. Attivo	<input type="radio"/>				
21. Stanco	<input type="radio"/>				
22. Irascibile	<input type="radio"/>				
23. Vigile	<input type="radio"/>				
24. Incerto	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix III: Italian version of the VAS-M questionnaire administered during the experimental sessions.

VAS scale

Quanto affaticato ti senti in questo momento?

Sposta il cursore sulla seguente scala che più corrisponde alla tua esperienza. Nota che ogni scala presenta, alle sue estremità, due aggettivi che la descrivono.

FATICA MENTALE

PER NIENTE AFFATICATO.....ESTREMAMENTE AFFATICATO

Appendix IV: Italian version of the NASA-TLX questionnaire administered during the experimental sessions to detect subjective perception of workload after the cognitive tasks.

NASA-TLX - COMPITO MENTALE

Siamo interessati ad esaminare il "carico di lavoro" che hai provato durante il COMPITO FISICO. Per fare questo abbiamo sviluppato una serie di sei scale di valutazione. Ti chiediamo gentilmente di leggere con attenzione le descrizioni delle scale. Per qualsiasi domanda siamo a tua disposizione.

In ognuna delle sei scale ti verrà chiesto di cerchiare la linea che più corrisponde all'esperienza vissuta durante il compito.

Ogni scala presenta, alle sue estremità, due aggettivi che la descrivono. Nota che la scala di valutazione sulla prestazione va da "buona" (sinistra) a "scarsa" (destra) e questo ordine ha confuso diverse persone in precedenza. Considera ciascuna scala individualmente e le tue risposte attentamente. La tua valutazione ha un ruolo molto importante nelle misurazioni che stiamo conducendo.

RICHIESTA MENTALE Quanto dispendioso è stato il compito da un punto di vista mentale?

Molto bassa.....**Molto Alta**

RICHIESTA FISICA Quanto dispendioso è stato il compito da un punto di vista fisico?

Molto bassa.....**Molto Alta**

RICHIESTA TEMPORALE Quanto affrettato è stato il ritmo del compito?

Molto bassa.....**Molto Alta**

PRESTAZIONE Quanto bravo sei stato a fare il compito che ti è stato richiesto?

Perfetto.....**Un fallimento**

SFORZO Quanto duramente ti sei dovuto impegnare per svolgere il compito?

Molto basso.....**Molto alto**

FRUSTRAZIONE Quanto sei stato insicuro, scoraggiato, irritato, stressato e infastidito?

Molto basso.....**Molto alto**

Appendix IV: Italian version of the BORG RRPE scale administered during the cycling exercises to detect subjective rating of perceived exertion.

- 6 Nessun impegno
- 7 Estremamente leggero
- 8
- 9 Molto leggero
- 10
- 11 Leggero
- 12
- 13 Moderato
- 14
- 15 Faticoso
- 16
- 17 Molto faticoso
- 18
- 19 Estremamente faticoso
- 20 Sforzo massimo